

Chemistry project

Study of acidity of fruits and Vegetable juices

name : Maryam

Twelve

Senior year research

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Primarily, I would like to thank god for making it possible to complete this project . then would like to express my utmost thankfulness and gratitude to my chemistry teacher Mrs Manju Sajeer who gave me the golden opportunity and provided support to complete this project.

Their suggestions and instructions has served as a major contribution in the completion of this project.

I would also like to thank my parents and friends who have helped me with their valuable suggestions . their guidance have been helpful in various phases for the completion of this project.

CONTENTS

01

Introduction

02

Chemical apparatus

03

Test for acidity

04

Test for iron

05

Test for carbohydrates

06

Test for starch

07

Conclusion

08

Bibliography

INTRODUCTION

Fruits and vegetables are important sources of dietary vitamins and minerals, which are essential for various physiological processes of our body. They contain free acids like citric acid in citric fruits; the acids ionize in solution giving H^+ ions.

The pH scale ranges from 0-14. pH greater than 7 indicates basic solution, pH less than 7 indicates acidic and that of 7 indicates a neutral solution.

In this study we aim to experiment and determine the acidic nature of different fruits and vegetable juices

CHEMICAL APPARATUS

TEST FOR ACIDITY

AIM: To detect the acidity of fruit juices and vegetable juices

THEORY: The presence of fats, carbohydrates and proteins in any food are detected by performing tests with the extract of the food. The vegetables and fruits are tested for these with the help of tests such as Fehling's test, Tollen's test etc. test for minerals are also performed.

PROCEDURE: The vegetable juices are diluted using distilled water . test for food substances are taken down with the solution

TEST: Take 5 ml of juice in a test tube and the pH value should be noted down by dipping it in the test tube. If the pH is less than 7 it is acidic or else the juice is basic

■ VEGETABLE JUICE

EXPERIMENT	VEGETABLE	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
Dip the pH indicator into a glass of cabbage juice . compare the colour of pH indicator to pH chart.	CABBAGE	Cabbage juice has a pH of 5.5 to 6.8	Acidic
	KALE	Kale juice has a pH of 6.4 to 6.8	acidic
	POTATO	Potato juice has a pH of 5.8 to 6.0	Acidic
	RADDISH	Raddish juice has a pH of 6 to 7	Acidic and strongly alkaline

FRUIT JUICE

EXPERIMENT	FFUITS	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
Dip the pH indicator into a glass of cranberry juice. Compare the colour of pH indicator to pH chart	cranberry	Cranberry juice has a pH of 2.3 to 2.5	acidic
	plum	Plum juice has a pH of 2.8 to 3.0	acidic
	mango	Mango juice has a pH of 5.8 to 6.0	acidic
	avacado	Avocado juice has a pH of 6.3 to 6.6	acidic

- **RESULT:** Most fruits and vegetables are acidic in nature. One must not only depend on fruits and vegetables for a balanced diet

TEST FOR IRON

- **AIM:** To detect iron in Fruit and vegetable juices
- **THEORY:** The presence of fats, carbohydrates and proteins in any food are detected by performing tests with the extract of the food. The vegetables and fruits are tested for these with the help of tests such as Fehling's test, Tollen's test etc. test for minerals are also performed.
- **PROCEDURE:** The vegetable juices are diluted using distilled water. test for food substances are taken down with the solution

VEGETABLE JUICES

EXPERIMENT	VEGETABLES	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
Take 2ml of juice, add 1 drop of conc nitric acid and boil the solution. Cool and add 2-3 drops of potassium sulphocyanide solution	Potato	Blood red colour	Presence of iron
	Cucumber	Blood red colour	Presence of iron
	Spinach	Blood red colour	Presence of iron
	Broccoli	Blood red colour	Presence of iron

▪ **FRUIT JUICES**

EXPERIMENT	FRUITS	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
Take 2ml of juice, add 1 drop of conc nitric acid and boil the solution. Cool and add 2-3 drops of potassium sulphocyanide solution	Orange	Blood red colour	Presence of iron
	Banana	Blood red colour	Presence of iron
	Apple	Blood red colour	Presence of iron
	Guava	Blood red colour	Presence of iron

- **RESULT:** From the above two tables we can conclude that most of the fruits and vegetable juices contain iron in them either in very high or low levels

TEST FOR CARBOHYDRATES

- **AIM:** To detect the presence of carbohydrates in Fruit and vegetable juices
- **THEORY:** The presence of fats, carbohydrates and proteins in any food are detected by performing tests with the extract of the food. The vegetables and fruits are tested for these with the help of tests such as Fehling's test, Tollen's test etc. test for minerals are also performed.
- **PROCEDURE:** The vegetable juices are diluted using distilled water. test for food substances are taken down with the solution
- **Test for carbohydrates:** Formation of red precipitate confirms the presence of reducing sugars like maltose, glucose, lactose. and fructose.

Blue \Rightarrow Negative test

Aldehyde and α - hydroxy ketone are absent

Red \Rightarrow Positive test

Aldehyde and α - hydroxy ketone are present

VEGETABLE JUICES

EXPERIMENT	VEGETABLES	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
1. Add 1-2 ml of Fehling's solution A and B to 2 ml of carrot juice. Keep the test tube in boiling water bath	Carrot	Red colour precipitate is obtained	Carbohydrates are present in carrot
2. Add 1-2 ml of Fehling's solution A and B to 2 ml of beetroot juice. Keep the test tube in boiling water bath	Beetroot	Red colour precipitate is obtained	Carbohydrates are present in Beetroot
3. Add 1-2 ml of Fehling's solution A and B to 2 ml of spinach juice. Keep the test tube in boiling water bath	Spinach	No red colour precipitate is formed	Carbohydrates are absent in spinach
4. Add 1-2 ml of Fehling's solution A and B to 2 ml of broccoli juice. Keep the test tube in boiling water bath	Broccoli	No red colour precipitate is formed	Carbohydrates are absent in broccoli

FRUIT JUICES

EXPERIMENT	FRUITS	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
1. Add 1-2 ml of Fehling's solution A and B to 2 ml of tomato juice. Keep the test tube in boiling water bath	Tomato	Red colour precipitate is obtained	Carbohydrates are present
2. Add 1-2 ml of Fehling's solution A and B to 2 ml of banana juice. Keep the test tube in boiling water bath	Banana	Red colour precipitate is obtained	Carbohydrates are present
3. Add 1-2 ml of Fehling's solution A and B to 2 ml of grape juice. Keep the test tube in boiling water bath	Grape	red colour precipitate is formed	Carbohydrates are present
4. Add 1-2 ml of Fehling's solution A and B to 2 ml of apple juice. Keep the test tube in boiling water bath	Apple	red colour precipitate is formed	Carbohydrates are present

▪ CHEMICAL EQUATIONS:

- **RESULT:** From the above two tables we can conclude that most of the fruits and vegetable juices contain carbohydrates in them either in very high or low levels

TEST FOR STARCH

- **AIM:** To detect the presence of starch in Fruit and vegetable juices
-
- **THEORY:** The presence of fats, carbohydrates and proteins in any food are detected by performing tests with the extract of the food. The vegetables and fruits are tested for these with the help of tests such as Fehling's test, Tollen's test, etc. Test for minerals are also performed.
- **PROCEDURE:** The vegetable juices are diluted using distilled water. Test for food substances are taken down with the solution
- **TEST FOR STARCH:** Peel off the skin of the fruits and vegetables and cut them into small pieces. Filter the extract and test the clear extract/ juice off the fruits and vegetables. Transfer the extracted juice to a test tube and label the tube with the name and type of the fruit. Take 2 ml of juice in the test tube and to it add a few drops of iodine solution. Swirl the test tube and look for any colour change to blue or black. Change of colour to blue, dark blue or black indicates the presence of starch.

VEGETABLE JUICES

EXPERIMENT	VEGETABLES	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
1. Add 1-2 drops of iodine solution to 2ml of cucumber juice taken in a test tube	Cucumber	The solution does not become blue black in colour	Starch is absent
2. Add 1-2 drops of iodine solution to 2ml of carrot juice taken in a test tube	Carrot	The solution does not become blue black in colour	Starch is absent
3. Add 1-2 drops of iodine solution to 2ml of spinach juice taken in a test tube	Spinach	The solution does not become blue black in colour	Starch is absent
4. Add 1-2 drops of iodine solution to 2ml of potato juice taken in a test tube	potato	The solution becomes blue black in colour	Starch is present

○ FRUIT JUICES

EXPERIMENT	FRUITS	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
1. Add 1-2 drops of iodine solution to 2ml of Tomato juice taken in a test tube	Tomato	The solution does not become blue black in colour	Starch is absent
2. Add 1-2 drops of iodine solution to 2ml of banana juice taken in a test tube	Banana	The solution becomes blue black in colour	Starch is present
3. Add 1-2 drops of iodine solution to 2ml of orange juice taken in a test tube	Orange	The solution does not become blue black in colour	Starch is absent
4. Add 1-2 drops of iodine solution to 2ml of guava juice taken in a test tube	Guava	The solution becomes blue black in colour	Starch is present

- **RESULT:** From the above two tables we can conclude that most of the fruits and vegetable juices contain carbohydrates in them either in very high or low levels

THE IODINE TEST FOR STARCH

CONCLUSION

After analyzing the vegetables and fruits it can be concluded that all of them contain one or the other compound vital for the body functioning. As fruits and vegetables are known to be full of vitamins, minerals and antioxidant and plant compounds that can protect us from diseases.

From the experiments it is observed that carbohydrate is a predominant constituent while fats being not required as much is introduced in the tested items. It is a merit as living organisms require carbohydrates the most commonly for generating energy. Among minerals present, calcium is present considerable as it is present in all the selected items whereas iron and starch are present sufficiently. Many other minerals are also present but in trace quantities as body requires them less.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- <https://thechemistryguru.com/>
- <https://www.wikihow.com/Test-for-Starch>
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Iodine%E2%80%93starch_test
- <https://byjus.com/chemistry/fehling>
- <https://www.vedantu.com/chemistry/fehling-test>